

DEDICATION

This project is dedicated to the glory of God.

CERTIFICATION

I certify that this project work ^{was} done by AJAYI OLUWASHINA SAMSON of the Department of Physics, University of Ado – Ekiti in partial fulfillment of the award of B.Sc (Hons) PHYSICS under my supervision.

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ABSTRACT

This project determines the chemical compositions of Ekiti Tantalite and Niobite and their electrical behaviour. These chemical compositions determined via XRF (X-ray fluorescence) technique. This is considered a sensitive experiment method to know their chemical compositions and concentrations ranging from few ppm to nearly 100 percent. The accurate knowledge of the elements which are present in these materials play a major role in their electrical behaviours.

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1.0 WHAT IS XRF (X-RAY FLUORESCENCE)

XRF is an analytical method to determine the chemical composition of all kinds of materials. The materials can be in solid, liquid, powder, filtered or other form. XRF can also sometimes be used to determine the thickness and composition of layers and coatings.

The method is fast, accurate and non-destructive and usually requires only a minimum of sample preparation. Industrial applications are very broad and include the metal, cement, oil, polymer, plastic and food industries, along with mining, mineralogy and geology, and environmental analysis of water and waste materials. XRF is also a very useful analysis technique for research in pharmacy.

Spectrometer systems can be divided into two main groups: energy dispersive systems (EDXRF) and wavelength dispersive systems (WDXRF). The elements that can be analyzed and their detection levels mainly depend on the spectrometer system used. The elemental range for EDXRF goes from sodium to uranium (Na to U). For WDXRF it is even wider, from Beryllium to Uranium (Be to U). The concentration range goes from (sub) ppm levels to 100%. Generally, the elements with high atomic numbers have better detection limits than the lighter elements.

The precision and reproducibility of XRF analysis is very high. Very accurate results are possible when good standards are available, but also for applications where no specific standards can be found.

The measurement time depends on the number of elements to be determined and the required accuracy, and varies between seconds and 30 minutes. The analysis time after the measurement is only a few seconds.

The figure 1 below shows what a spectrum looks like. The peak profiles are clearly visible. The positions of the peaks determine the elements present in the sample, while the heights of the peaks determines the concentrations.

Figure 1. Typical spectrum of a soil sample measured with an EDXRF spectrometer

1.1 BASICS OF XRF

In XRF, X-rays produced by a source irradiate a sample. In most cases the source is an X-ray tube. The elements present in the sample will emit fluorescent X-ray radiation with discrete energies (equivalent to colour for optical light) that are characteristic for these elements. A different energy is equivalent to a different colour. By measuring the energies (determining the colours) of the radiation emitted by the sample it is possible to determine

which elements are present. This step is called Qualitative Analysis. By measuring the intensities of the emitted energies (colours) it is possible to determine how much of each element is present in the sample. This step is called Quantitative Analysis.

1.2 WHAT ARE X-RAYS

X-rays can be seen as electromagnetic (E.M) waves with their associated wavelengths, or as beams of photons with associated energies. Both views are correct, but one or the other is easier to understand depending on the phenomena to be explained. Other electromagnetic waves include light, radio waves and gamma – rays. Figure 2 shows that X-rays have wavelengths and energies between gamma-rays and ultraviolet light. The wavelengths of X – rays are in the range from 0.01 to 10nm, which corresponds to energies in the range from 0.125 to 125 KeV. The wavelengths of X – rays is inversely proportional to its energy; according to $E\lambda = hc$, E is the energy in KeV and λ the wavelength in nm. The term hc is the product of planck's constant and the velocity of light and has, using KeV and nm as units, a constant value of 1.23985.

Figure 2. X – rays and other electromagnetic radiations

1.3. INTERACTION OF X RAYS WITH MATTER

There are three main interactions of X-rays with matter: Fluorescence, Compton Scatter, and Rayleigh Scatter. IF X –rays fall on material a fraction will pass through the sample, a fraction is absorbed by the sample and produces fluorescent radiation, and a fraction is scattered back. Scattering can occur with loss of energy and without loss of energy. The first is called Compton Scattering and the second Rayleigh Scattering. The fluorescence and the scatter depend on the thickness (d), density (ρ) and composition of the material and on the energy of the X-rays. The next sections will describe the production of fluorescent radiation and scatter.

Figure 3. Three main interaction of X-ray with matter

1.4 THE PHYSICS OF FLUORESCENT RADIATION

The classical model of an atom is a nucleus with positively charged protons and non-charge neutrons, surrounded by electrons grouped in shells

or orbitals. The innermost shell is called the K-shell, followed by L-shells, M-shells etc travelling outwards. The L – shell has 3 sub – shells called LI, LII and LIII. The M – shell has 5 sub – shells M_I , M_{II} , M_{III} , M_{IV} and M_V . The K – shell can contain 2 electrons, the L- shell 8 and the M – shell 18. The energy electron has depends on the shell it is in, and on the element to which it belongs. Irradiating an atom with particles like X – ray photons and electrons with sufficient energy can expel an electron from the atom (figure 4).

Figure 4. Production of characteristic radiation

This produces a hole in a shell, in the example a hole in the K- shell, putting the atom in an unstable situation with a higher energy. The atom wants to restore the original configuration, and this is done by transferring an electron from an outer shell e.g. the L – shell to the hole in K – shell. An L – shell electron has a higher energy than a K – shell electron, and when an L – shell electron is transferred to the K shell, the energy surplus is emitted as X – rays. In a spectrum this is seen as a line. The energy of the emitted X-rays depends on the difference in energy of the shell with the initial hole and the

energy of the electron that fills the hole (in the example, the difference between the energy of the K-shell and L-shell). Each atom has its specific energy levels, so the emitted radiation is characteristic for that atom. An atom emits more than just one more line because different holes can be produced and different electrons can fill up these holes. The collection of emitted lines is characteristic for the element and is more or less a fingerprint of the element.

To expel an electron from an atom, the X – rays must have a higher energy than the binding energy of the electron. If an electron is expelled, the incoming radiation is absorbed and the higher the absorption the higher the fluorescence. If on the other hand the energy is too high, many photons will ‘pass’ the atom and only a few electrons will be removed. Figure 5 shows that high energies are hardly absorbed and produce low fluorescence. If the energy is lower and comes closer to the binding energy of the K – shell electrons, more and more radiation is absorbed. The highest yield is reached when the energy of the photon is just above the binding energy of the electron to be expelled. If the energy becomes lower than the binding energy, a jump or edge can be seen: the energy is too low to expel electrons from that shell, but is too high to expel electrons from the lower energetic shells. The figures show the K edge corresponding to the K – shell, and three L edges corresponding with L_I , L_{II} , L_{III} shells.

Fig. 5. Absorption versus energy

Not all incoming photons produce fluorescent photons. The fluorescence yield is the ratio of the emitted photons and the number of incoming photons. Figure 6 shows the fluorescence yield for K and L lines as functions of the atomic number Z . The figure clearly shows that the yield is low for the very light elements, explaining why it is so difficult to measure these elements.

Figure 6. Fluorescence yield for K and L electrons

There are several ways to indicate different lines. The Siegbahn and IUPAC notations are the two most found in literature. The Siegbahn notation indicates a line by the symbol of an element followed by the name of the shell where the initial hole is and Greek letter (α, β, γ etc.) indicating the

relative intensity of a line. eg. Fe - $K\alpha$, is the strongest iron line due to an expelled K electron. The Siegbahn notation however does not tell from which shell the electron comes that fills the hole. In the IUPAC notation, a line is indicated by the element and the shell where the initial hole was, followed by the shell where the electron comes from that fills up this hole. For example Cr - KL_{III} is chromium radiation due to a hole produced in the K-shell filled by an electron in the L_{III} shell. Generally, K - lines are more intense than L - lines which are more intense than M - lines and so on. Quantum mechanics teaches that not all transitions are allowed, for instance a transition from the L_I to the K - shell. Figure 7 gives an overview of the most important lines with their transitions.

Fig. 7. Major lines and their transitions

1.5. ABSORPTION AND ENHANCEMENT EFFECTS

To reach the atoms inside the sample the X - rays have to pass the layer above it, and this layer will absorb a part of the incoming radiation. The

characteristic radiation produced also has to pass this layer to leave the sample, and again part of the radiation will be absorbed.

Figure. 8. Absorption of Incoming and Fluorescence X – rays

The magnitude of the absorption depends on the energy of the radiation, the path length of the sample that have to be passed, and the density of the sample. The absorption increases as the path length, density and atomic number of the elements in the layer increase, and as the energy of the radiation decreases. The absorption can be so high that the elements deeper in the sample are not reached by the incoming radiation or the characteristic radiation can no longer leave the sample. This means that only elements close to the surface will be measured.

The incoming radiation are X – rays, and the characteristic radiation emitted by atoms in the sample itself are also X – rays. The fluorescent X – rays are sometimes able to expel electrons from other elements in the sample. This, as with the X – rays coming from the source, results in fluorescent radiation. The characteristic radiation produced directly by the X – rays coming from the source is called primary fluorescence, while that produced

by the sample due to primary fluorescence of other atom is called secondary fluorescence.

Fig. 9. Primary and Secondary Fluorescence

A spectrometer will measure the sum of the primary and secondary fluorescence, and it is impossible to distinguish between both contribution. The contribution of secondary fluorescence to the characteristic radiation can be significant (in the order of 20%). Similarly, tertiary and even higher order radiation can occur. In almost all practical situations these are negligible, but in very specific cases can reach values of 3%.

1.6. ABSORPTION AND ANALYSIS DEPTHS

As the sample gets thicker and thicker, more and more radiation is absorbed. Finally, radiation produced in the deeper layers of the sample is no longer able to leave the sample. When this limit is reached; depends on the material and on the energy of the radiation.

Table I gives the approximate analysis depth in various materials for three lines with different energies. Mg $K\alpha$ has an energy of 1.25 KeV, Cr $K\alpha$ 5.41 KeV and Sn $K\alpha$ 25.19 KeV.

Material	Mg K α	Cr K α	Sn K α
Lead	0.7 μ m	4.5 μ m	55 μ m
Iron	1 μ m	35 μ m	290 μ m
SiO ₂	8 μ m	110 μ m	0.9cm
Li ₂ B ₄ O ₇	13 μ m	900 μ m	4.6cm
H ₂ O	16 μ m	1000 μ m	5.3cm

When a sample is measured, only the atoms within the analysis depth are analyzed. If samples and standards with various thicknesses are analyzed, the thickness has to be taken into account.

1.7. RAYLEIGH AND COMPTON SCATTERING

A part of the incoming X – rays is scattered (reflected) by the sample instead of producing characteristic radiation. Scatter happens when a photon hits an electron and is bounced away. The photon loses a fraction of its energy, which is taken over by the electron as shown in figure 10. It can be compared with one billiard ball colliding with another. After the collision, the first ball lost a part of its energy to the ball that was hit. The fraction that is lost depends on the angle at which the electron (ball) was hit. This type of scattering is called Compton or incoherent scattering.

Fig. 10. Compton Scattering

Another phenomenon is Rayleigh scattering. This happens when photons collide with strongly bound electrons. The electrons stay in their shell but start oscillating at the frequency of the incoming radiation. Due to this oscillation, the electrons will emit radiation at the same frequency (energy) as the incoming radiation. This gives the impression that the incoming radiation is reflected (scattered) by the atom. This type of scattering is called Rayleigh or coherent scattering.

Fig. 11. Rayleigh Scattering

Samples with light elements will give rise to high Compton scattering and low Rayleigh scattering because they have many loosely bound electrons. When the elements get heavier the scattering reduces. For the

heavy elements the Compton scattering disappear, and only Rayleigh scattering remains.

1.8 POLARIZATION

X – rays are electromagnetic waves with electric and magnetic components E and B. This discussion is limited to the electrical component E but also holds for the magnetic component B. the amplitude of the electromagnetic waves determines the intensity of the X – rays. Electromagnetic waves are transverse waves, which means that the electrical component is perpendicular to the propagation direction.

X – rays are said to be linearly polarized if the electrical components are all in one plane. If the electrical component has no preferred direction the waves are non – polarized.

An electrical component E pointing in any direction can always be resolved into two perpendicular directions. Figure 12 shows how a component is resolved in a vertical and a horizontal direction.

Fig. 12. Electrical component resolved horizontal and vertical components

If non – polarized X – rays are reflected (scattered) by a specimen through 90° , the reflected X – rays will be polarized in one direction. Figure

13 (left) shows that the vertical electrical component is not reflected because this would point in the new propagation direction. What remains after one reflection is the horizontal component alone, and the scattered X-rays are polarized horizontally.

Figure 13 (right) shows what happens if the X-rays are scattered again but perpendicular to the previous direction. In the second reflection the horizontal component is not reflected because it would point in the new propagation direction. Nothing is left from the incoming radiation after two perpendicular reflections. This feature is used in EDXRE spectrometers to eliminate the background profile from a spectrum.

Figure 13. Polarization after 1 and 2 reflections

2.0. THE XRF SPECTROMETER

The basic concept for all spectrometers is a source, a sample and a detection system. The source irradiates a sample, and a detector measures the radiation coming from the sample.

Figure 14: Basic Designs of EDXRF and WDXRF Spectrometers

In most cases the source is an X – ray tube, and our discussion will only centre on such spectrometers (alternative types use a radioactive source or synchrotron). Spectrometer systems are generally divided into two main groups: energy dispersive systems (EDXRF) and wavelength dispersive systems (WDXRF). The difference between the two systems is found the detection system.

EDXRF Spectrometer have a detector that is able to measure the different energies of the characteristic radiation coming directly from the sample. The detector can radiation from the elements in the sample. This separation is called dispersion.

WDXRF spectrometers use an analyzing crystal to disperse the different energies. All radiation coming from the sample falls on the crystal. The crystal diffracts the different energies into different directions, similar to a prism that disperses different colours into different directions.

2.1 EDXRF SPECTROMETERS

EDXRF spectrometers can be divided into spectrometers with 2D and 3D optics. Both types have a source and an energy dispersive detector, but the difference is found in the X – ray optical path. For 2D spectrometers the X – ray path is in one plane , (2 dimension). For the 3D spectrometers, the path is not limited to one plane but in 3 dimensions.

2.2. EDXRF SPECTROMETERS WITH 2D OPTICS

The simplest configuration is shown in figure 15 (left). The tube irradiates the sample directly, and the fluorescence coming from the sample is measured with an energy dispersive detector. An alternative is to place a secondary target between the tube and the sample as shown in figure 15 (right). The tube irradiates the secondary target and this target will emits its characteristic radiation. The advantage of a secondary target is that it emits (almost) mono – chromatic radiation but its disadvantage is that energy is lost. Using different secondary targets can achieve optimum excitation for all elements.

The detector is able to measure the energies of the incoming radiation directly. Besides the fluorescence, scattered tube radiation will reach the detector, which results in a background profile and background noise. Due to this background, it is difficult to detect low peaks and as a result to determine low concentrations. The X – ray path is in one plane, so is 2 – dimensional, and the X – ray optics are called 2D optics.

Figure 15. Energy dispersive spectrometers with 2D optics and direct excitation (left) and polarized optics (3D) with indirect excitation right.

2.3 EDXRF SPECTROMETERS WITH 3D OPTICS

Figure 16 shows an EDXRF spectrometer using 3D optics. The X – ray path is not in one plane but in two perpendicular planes, and the optics for this type of spectrometers is called 3D optics. The tube irradiates a secondary target, which emits its characteristic X – rays and scatters a part of the incoming X – rays. The radiation coming from the target is used to irradiate the sample, so for the sample the target behaves like a source. The sample emits its characteristic radiation, which is measured by an energy dispersive detector.

Fig. 16. Energy Dispersive Spectrometer with 3D Optics and Indirect Excitation.

The advantage of this geometry is that scattered tube radiation cannot reach the detector because of polarization. To reach the detector, the tube radiation must scatter in 2 perpendicular directions, but as explained in (fig. 15); the X – rays vanish after two perpendicular reflections. As a consequence, the radiation coming from the tube will not reach the detector. This will result in a very low background in the spectrum and makes it possible to detect very weak peaks, and hence to determine very low concentrations.

The characteristic radiation of the target is partly scattered by the sample and reaches the detector. This radiation is scattered in only one direction and so it will not vanish.

2.4 WDXRF SPECTROMETERS

The first part of a WDXRF spectrometer is equivalent to an EDXRF spectrometer with 2D optics and without a secondary target. The tube irradiates a sample and the radiation coming from the sample is detected. The detection system is different from EDXRF spectrometers.

For WDXRF, the detection system is a set of collimators, a diffraction crystal and a detector. The X – rays coming from the sample fall on the crystal, and the crystal diffracts (reflects) the X – rays with different wavelength (energies) in different directions (This is equivalent to a prism that separates white light into its different colours). By placing the detector at a certain angle, the intensity of X – rays with a certain wavelength can be measured. It is also possible to mount the detector on a goniometer and

move it through an angular range to measure the intensities of many different wavelengths. Spectrometers that use a moving detector on a goniometer are called sequential spectrometers, because they measure the intensities of the different wavelengths one after another.

2.5. COMPARISON OF EDXRF AND WDXRF SPECTROMETERS

EDXRF and WDXRF have their advantages and disadvantages

(Table 2).

	EDXRF	WDXRF
Elementary range	(Sodium to Uranium)	(Beryllium to Uranium)
Detection limit	Less optimal for light elements and good for heavy elements	Good for Beryllium and all heavier elements
Sensitivity	Less optimal for light elements. Good for heavy elements	Reasonable for light elements. Good for heavy elements .
Resolution	Less optimal for light elements Good for heavy elements.	Good for light elements. Less optimal for heavy elements.
Cost	Relatively inexpensive	Relatively expensive
Power Consumption	5- 1000W	200 – 4000W
Measurement	Simultaneous	Sequential/simultaneous
Critical Moving Parts	No	Crystal, Goniometer

2.6. X – RAY TUBES

The basic design of an X – ray tube is shown in figure 17. It contains a filament (wire) and an anode (target) placed in a vacuum housing. An electrical current heats up the filament and electrons are emitted. A high

voltage (20 – 100KV) is applied across the filament and the anode, and this high voltage accelerates the electrons towards the anode. When the electrons hit the anode they are decelerated, which causes the emission of X – rays. This radiation is called Brems - Strahlung ('Brems' is German for decelerate, 'Strahlung' for radiation). The energy and intensity of the emitted X – rays is uniform, but a spectrum of energies each with its own intensity is emitted. This part of spectrum is often called the continuum, because it is a continuous band of emitted energies.

Figure 17. Basic Design of a Side – window X – ray Tube

A fraction of the electrons that hit the atoms in the anode will expel electrons from these atoms, causing emission of characteristic radiation. The energy of this radiation is determined by the element(s) in the anode.

The X – rays emitted by the anode can leave the tube through a Beryllium (Be) window. The continuum of an X – ray tube depends on the applied KV, the MA and on the material used for the anode.

These tubes are called side – window tubes because the Beryllium window is at the side of the tube housing. It is also possible to rearrange the

filament and the anode, and have a window at the end of the tube (an end – window tube). An alternative design is shown in figure 18. The electrons hit the anode on one side, the opposite side, and the radiation leaves the tube through the Be – window. These tubes are called Target Transmission tubes.

Figure 18. Design of a Target Transmission Tube.

2.7 SECONDARY TARGETS

A secondary target is irradiated by a source and emits its characteristic radiation in a similar way to the target (anode) in the tube. It will also scatter a part of the incoming radiation. The target act as a source, and the radiation coming from the target is used to irradiate the sample. There are three types of secondary targets: Fluorescent targets, Barkla targets Bragg targets.

2.8 FLUORESCENT TARGETS

Fluorescent targets use the fluorescence of elements in the target to excite the sample. These target also scatter the tube radiation, but the fluorescence dominates. Scatter is low because the targets (mainly) contain heavy elements.

The tube irradiates the target, and the element(s) in the target emit their characteristic fluorescent radiation. This radiation falls on the sample, causing fluorescent radiation. For highest fluorescence in the sample, the energy of the X – rays coming from the target must be just above the binding energy of the electrons of the elements in the sample. Spectrometers can be equipped with a set of different targets, and optimum fluorescence is achieved by selecting the correct target.

2.9. BARKLA TARGETS

Barkla target use scattered tube radiation to excite the sample. These targets also fluoresce but the energy or intensity of these lines is too low to excite elements in the sample. Barkla targets are made of light elements like Al_2O_3 and B_4C , because these give the highest scattered radiation.

Barkla targets scatter a wide energy spectrum and can be used to measure a large range of elements. Generally Barkla targets measure the heavier elements.

2.9.1 BRAGG TARGETS

Bragg targets are crystal that reflect only one specific energy in a certain direction. By mounting the crystal between the tube and the sample it is possible to select a single tube line irradiate the sample, with no other radiation diffracted towards the sample. This will reduce the background and improve the detection limit. If the spacing of the planes in the crystal is such that the tube line is diffracted at an angle of 90° , it can be used in 3D optics as a perfect polarized.

3.0. DETECTORS AND MULTI CHANNEL ANALYZERS

Different types of detectors are used in XRF. EDXRF mainly uses solid – state detectors where WDXRF uses gas – filled detectors and scintillation detectors. The EDXRF detector is a wide – range detector and measures all elements from Na (sodium) up to U (uranium). Gas – filled detectors measure elements from Be to Cu (Beryllium to Copper) and the scintillation detector from Cu up to U (Copper to Uranium). All these detectors produce an electrical pulse when an X – ray photon enters the detectors, and the height of this pulse is proportional to the energy of the incoming photon. The pulses are amplified and then counted by a Multi Channel Analyzer.

There are three important properties of detection systems: resolution, sensitivity and dispersion.

Resolution is the ability of the detector to distinguish between different energy levels. A high resolution means that the detector can distinguish between many different energies.

Sensitivity indicates how efficiently incoming photons, are counted. If for instance a detector is very thin, incoming photons may pass it without producing a pulse against the number of incoming photons is high.

Dispersion indicates the ability of the detector to separate x – rays with different energies. A high dispersion means that different energies are separated well.

→ to this, the incoming X –

3.1. MULTI CHANNEL ANALYZER (MCA)

The MCA counts how many pulses are generated in each height interval. The number of pulses of a certain height gives the intensity of the corresponding energy. The ability of the detector and MCA to distinguish between different energies is called the resolution.

Figure 19. MCA makes a histogram of the energy of the detected photons.

Strictly speaking a WDXRF only has to count pulses and does not have to distinguish between their heights, because the crystal has already selected X – ray with one specific energy. In practical situations the MCA for a WDXRF detector is able to distinguish 100 – 255 different energy levels.

In EDXRF spectrometers, the detector and MCA are able to distinguish between 1000 and 1600 different energy levels. This is sufficient to analyze spectra and to separate the radiation of the elements in a sample.

3.2 ESCAPE PEAKS AND PILE – UP PEAKS

Detectors suffer from two artefacts: escape peaks and pile – up peaks. The atoms in the detector (Ar, Si Ge) will also emit their own characteristic

radiation when hit by the incoming X – rays. Due to this, the incoming X – rays will lose a part of their energy, which is equivalent to the energy of the line of the detector element. For Si this is about 1.7 KeV, for Ge 10 KeV and for Ar about 3 KeV. Besides counting photons with the initial energy, the detector will also therefore count a fraction with a lower energy. In the spectrum this will result in two peaks: a main peak and an escape peak.

Pile – up or sum peaks are the result of 2 photons that enter the detector simultaneously. Both photons will produce a cloud of electrons, but they are detected as one large Cloud. The energy detected is equivalent to the sum of the two initial energies.

3.3 COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT DETECTORS

The resolution of gas – filed and scintillation detectors is very poor, and they are not suited for energy dispersive spectrometers. They can however be used in wavelength dispersive spectrometers, because in these instruments the resolution is achieved by the diffraction crystal. The sensitivity depends on the type of detector and on the energy of the incoming X – rays. Gas filled detectors have a high sensitivity for low energies and a low sensitivity for high energies and are so best suited to detect lower energies. The opposite applies for scintillation detectors, which are better suited for high energies than low energies and high resolution for the higher energies. EDXRF spectrometers commonly use solid – state detectors, while WDXRF spectrometers use a combination of gas – filled and scintillation detectors.

3.4. FILTERS

Filters are placed between source and sample. They reduce the intensity of interfering lines and background, and hence improve the signal to noise ratio. In 2D optics, a fraction of the scattered tube spectrum reaches the detector and will be present in the measured spectrum. In some cases the tube lines of the spectrum interfere with lines coming from the sample (for example, the Rh K lines coming from the tube can interfere with Ag and Cd K lines coming from the sample). By mounting a filter between tube and sample, the tube lines are absorbed and the lines coming from the sample are not.

Background radiation are also reduced by Filter. Then, the analytical lines can be determined with higher precision, and with lower detection limits. Commonly used filter materials are Aluminum and Brass with a thickness between 100 and 1000 μm , depending on the tube lines that have to be filtered out.

If the intensity is too high for the detector and this becomes saturated, a filter can absorb part of the radiation to prevent saturation.

3.5 DIFFRACTION CRYSTALS AND COLLIMATORS

A crystal can be seen as a stack of thin layers all having the same thickness, as shown in figure 20.

Fig. 20 Demonstration of Bragg's Law

If a parallel beam of X-rays fall on the crystal, the first layer reflects a fraction of the X-rays. The remaining radiation penetrates the crystal and is reflected by the subsequent layers. If the difference in path length between reflections from layers is a multiple of half the wavelength of the radiation, the two reflected beams vanish. If the difference is exactly an integer times the wavelength, the two reflected beams reinforce. The difference in path length is an integer times the wavelength and the following relation, called Bragg's law, holds.

$$n \cdot \lambda = 2 \cdot d \cdot \sin \theta$$

At an angle θ , all reflected radiation with a wavelength λ and obeying Bragg's law are 'in phase' and add up. All other wavelengths at the same angle will vanish.

A detector placed at angle θ can therefore measure the intensity of the corresponding wavelength. Reflected wavelength obeying Bragg's law for $n = 1$ are called first - order reflections, for $n = 2$ second - order etc. Note that at a specific angle radiation will be visible with wavelength $\lambda, \lambda/2, \lambda/3$, but the detector can distinguish between them.

At any specific angle, only radiation with a wavelength obeying Bragg's law is reflected. Radiation with slightly different wavelengths will be reflected at slightly different angles, but will still reach the detector and will interfere with the energy to be measured. A collimator, which is a set of parallel plates, is used to obtain a parallel X - ray beam that falls exactly at the required angle on the crystal. The primary collimator can be placed between the crystal and detector.

3.6 MASKS

A mask is a plate with a hole in it. The tube irradiates the sample, but also the cup in which the sample is placed. This cup will also emit its characteristic radiation, but must not reach the detector or it will interfere with the radiation coming from the sample. A mask is placed between the sample and the detection system so that the detector 'sees' only the sample.

3.7 SPINNER

Samples are not always perfectly homogenous and scratches on the surface may also influence measurements. A spinner rotates the sample during the measurement to even out effects of non – homogeneity and scratches.

3.8. VACUUM AND HELIUM SYSTEM

The source, sample and detection system are mounted in a vacuum chamber. Air will absorb tube radiation, especially low – energy radiation. This would make analysis of light elements impossible since all X – rays would be absorbed by air and not reach the detector. Liquids and wet powders cannot be measured in vacuum because they would evaporate. These types of sample are usually measured in a Helium filled spectrometer. Helium absorbs the radiation of the light elements, up to about fluorine, so it is not possible to measure these elements in liquids. Helium does not however affect the radiation from heavier elements.

4.0. XRF ANALYSIS

A good analysis starts with a well – prepared sample and a good measurement.

After a sample is measured, it is analyzed. This is done in two steps: qualitative analysis followed by quantitative analysis. Qualitative analysis determines which element are present and their net intensities form the measured spectra. In many routine situations, the elements in the sample are known and only the net intensities need to be determined. The net intensities

are used in the quantitative analysis to calculate the concentrations of the elements present.

EDXRF and WDXRF often use slightly different methods for qualitative analysis. In EDXRF the area of a peak gives the intensity while in WDXRF the height of the peak gives the intensity. Both methods would work for EDXRF and WDXRF, but both have their specific advantages and disadvantages.

4.1. SAMPLE PREPARATION

Often, only a small sample of material is analyzed, for instance in a steel plant, a small disk represents the full furnace contents the sample must be representative of the entire material, and so must be taken very carefully. Once taken, it must also be handled carefully, the sensitivity of modern spectrometers is so high that they even detect fingerprints, which can disturb the analysis. Another basic requirement is that the sample must be homogenous. Spectrometers only analyze the sample's surface layer, so it must be representative of the whole sample.

Most spectrometers are designed to measure samples that are circular disks with a radius between 5 and 50mm. The sample is placed in a cup, and the cup is placed in the spectrometer. Special supporting films allow the measurement of loose powders and liquids.

4.2 XRF MEASUREMENT

XRF is a very sensitive technique and samples must be clean. Even fingerprints on a sample can affect the result of the analysis. For accurate

results, the spectrometer (for example, the KV setting of the tube or the detector settings is tuned to the elements to be analyzed) bad settings can lead to poor results. In EDXRF a whole spectrum is measured simultaneously and the area of the peak profile determines the concentration of an element. Measuring the height of the peak profile is an alternative, but a lot of information would be lost, because the area of a peak profile is less sensitive for noise than the height of the same peak. In WDXRF it is common practice to measure only at the top of the peak profile. The positions of the peaks are known and measuring at the top position only gives the best accuracy and lowest measuring time.

4.3 OPTIMUM MEASUREMENT CONDITIONS

'Optimum' can be define in many different ways, and the definition depends on the criteria used. The criteria can be highest intensity, lowest background, minimum line overlap and many others. A high intensity and low background have the advantage that lines can be detected and measured accurately and quickly. Minimum line overlap has the advantage that the intensity of the lines can be determined directly, without sophisticated mathematical techniques. Weak lines can also be difficult to detect on the tails of strong lines.

The maximum intensity of a line is achieved if the energy of the incoming radiation is just above the absorption edge of that line. In WDXRF systems and EDXRF with direct excitation, this can be done by applying a

voltage to the tube so that the largest part of the tube spectrum (continuum or tube line) has an energy just above the absorption edge of the analytical line.

In EDXRF systems using secondary targets, it is done by using a target that has a fluorescent line with an energy just above the absorption edge of the analytical line. The voltage applied to the tube is such is such that the spectrum of the tube excites the element(s) in the target bed for WDXRF systems. If no such target is available, a Barkla target is used to scatter the total tube spectrum. The tube voltage is selected so that the largest part of the tube spectrum has an energy just above the absorption edge of the analytical line.

Line overlap occurs when the line of one elements overlaps the line of another elements. The interfering line can come from an element in the sample, but also from an element in the tube, crystal, secondary target, or any other component in the optical path.

High resolution and/or dispersion achieve minimum line overlap. In WDXRF spectrometers the crystal and collimator have a large effect on the line overlap, which can be minimized by selecting the proper crystal and collimator. In EDXRF spectrometers, the detector and MCA settings have a large effect on the resolution and must be selected carefully. In some cases it is also worth measuring a weaker line of an element if a strong line is overlapped and the weaker line is not. For spectrometers using secondary targets, the selection of the proper target is essential. Scattered target lines can interfere with the lines of the sample so selecting the target that gives the

lowest interference is advisable. Using a target that only excites the elements of interest and not elements that give interfering lines helps to reduce the line overlap.

4.4. QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS IN EDXRF

The first step in the analysis is to determine the top positions and the areas of the line profiles. The positions of the tops represent the presence of elements and the areas represent the intensities of the lines. Where the elements in a sample are known, only the intensities need to be determined. The quantitative analyses requires net intensities, meaning that the background must be subtracted from the spectrum.

4.5. PEAK SEARCH AND PEAK MATCH

Peak search and peak match are used to find which elements are present in the sample.

Peak search uses a mathematical technique to find the peaks in a spectrum. Peak match determines the elements to which the peak profiles belong. This is done by comparing the positions of the peaks to a database holding the positions of all possible lines.

4.6. QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS IN WDXRF PEAK SEARCH AND PEAK MATCH

As with EDXRF, peak search and peak match are used to discover which elements are present in the sample. Once again, peak search finds the

peaks, and peak match determines the associated elements by referring to a database.

4.7 MEASURING PEAK HEIGHT AND BACKGROUND SUBTRACTION

In WDXRF it is common practice to measure the intensity at the peak of a line and on a few background positions closer to the peak. The position must be chosen carefully and must be free of other peaks. The background under the peak is determined by interpolating the intensities measured at the background positions.

Figure 21. Determination of net intensity

4.8. LINE OVERLAP CORRELATION

Figure 22. shows two overlapping lines and their sum. Here, the height of the peak cannot be determined as the raw intensity minus the background.

Figure 22. Two overlapping peaks and their sum

The intensity measured at position 1 is the sum of the net height of peak 1 and a factor of peak 2, and vice versa. Mathematically this can be written as

$$R_1^m = R_1^n + f_{12} \cdot R_2^n$$

$$R_2^m = f_{21} \cdot R_1^n + R_2^n$$

This is a set of 2 linear equations, and the net intensities of both peaks can be calculated if the factors f_{12} and f_{21} are known. These two factors can be determined using a reference sample that contains only element 1, and another containing element 2. For element 2, such a sample will give a spectrum like that in figure 22.

Figure 22. Determination of overlapping factor

The fraction of peak 2 that overlaps with peak 1 is calculated as

$$f_{12} = \frac{R_{2,1}}{R_2}$$

The overlap factor ²¹ of line 1 on line 2 can be determine in the same way.

4.9. COUNTING STATISTICS AND DETECTION LIMITS

To detect a peak of an element, it must be significantly above the background noise. The noise depends on the number of X – ray photons counted. The lower the number of photons counted. The lower the number of photons counted, the higher the noise. The analysis is commonly done on the number of photons counted per second, but the noise depends on the total number of photons counted. By measuring for a longer period, it is possible to collect more photons and hence reduce the noise.

Figure 23

Figure 23. Shows three spectra of the same material, but with different measurement time. In the first spectrum it is difficult to determine the peaks and their heights. In the second, the peaks are more prominent and in the third they can be clearly seen and their net height can be determined accurately. A commonly accepted definition for the detection limit is that the net intensity of a peak must be 3 times higher than the standard deviation of the background noise. The standard deviation of the background noise equals the square root of the intensity (in counts), so elements are said to be detectable if

$$\sqrt{\frac{N_p}{N_b}} \geq 3 \quad \text{Where } N_p \text{ is the number of counts measured on the peak.}$$

N_b is the number of counts measured on the background. For low backgrounds, low line intensities are sufficient to fulfil the requirement, so a low background gives low detection limits. 3D optics is used to reduce the background.

4.9.1. QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS IN EDXRF AND WDXRF

Quantitative analysis is basically the same for EDXRF and WDXRF. The only difference is that in EDXRF the area of a peak gives the intensity, while in WDXRF the height of a peak gives the intensity. The exact same mathematical methods can be used to calculate the composition of samples.

In the qualitative Analysis, the net intensities are converted into concentrations. The usual procedure is to calibrate the spectrometer by measuring one or more reference materials. The calibration determines the relationship between the concentrations of elements and the intensity of the fluorescent lines of those elements. Unknown concentrations can be determined once the relationship is known. The intensities of the elements with unknown concentration are measured, with the corresponding concentration being determined from the calibration.

5.0. MATERIALS AND PROPERTIES

Tantalum and niobium are the major elements from minerals such as tantalite and niobite.

Tantalum and niobium are refractory metals, both metals are characterized by high melting points. Accelerated oxidation in air occurs at 425⁰c for tantalum and niobium, therefore protective coatings must be applied to these metals if they are to be used at higher temperature. Tensile and yield strength of these metals are substantially retained at higher temperature. The two metals are mutually soluble and form solid – solution

alloys with each other in any proportion. The pure form of the metals are ductile but niobium is also malleable. Tantalum is almost completely immune to chemical attack at temperature below 150⁰c, and is attacked only by hydrofluoric acid, acidic solutions containing the fluoride ion and free sulphur trioxide. Niobium and tantalum are highly resistant to corrosion.

The principal application of tantalum are in capacitor anodes, filaments, gettering devices, high – temperature aerospace engine components and due to its resistant to corrosion, it is used to make surgical instrument and medical equipment; in surgery as rods to stitch broken bones, skull plates and wire meshes to help repair nerves and muscles. Because it has such a very high melting point, it is alloyed with other metals to create alloys that are needed for very high temperature application.

Niobium on its part is used as superconducting materials, thin – film substrates, electrical contacts, heat sinks, jewelry and as an alloying addition in steels and superalloys.

However, the two metals are usually considered together because most of their working characteristics are similar. The two are so difficult to isolate from one another. Tantalum was named after Greek god, Tantalus. Niobium discovered before tantalum, was named after the daughter of Tantalus, Niobe. The table below gives some information on properties of Tantalum and Niobium.

Properties	ELEMENTS	
	TANTALUM	NIOBIUM
Symbol	Ta	Nb
Atomic number	73	41
Atomic weight(g)	180.9479	92.9064
Group number	5	5
Period number	6	5
Block	d – block	d – block
Colour	Grey – blue	Platinum white but turn blue on exposure to air
Classification	Metallic	Metallic
Isotopes	1 known Isotope	18 known isotope

Niobium (Niobe, daughter of Tantalus) Nb or columbium (columbia, name for America) Cb; melting points of $2468 \pm 10^0\text{c}$, boiling point 4742^0c , valence; 2,3,4,5. Discovered in 1801 by Hachette in an ore sent to England more than a century before by John winthrop the younger, first governor of Connecticut. The metal was first prepared in 1864 by Blomstrand, who reduced the chloride by heating it in a hydrogen atmosphere. The name 'niobioum' was adopted by IUPAC in 1950 after 100 years of controversy. Many leading chemical societies and government organization refer to it by

this name. Most metallurgist and leading metal societies, and all but one of the leading U.S. commercial producers, however still refer to the metal as 'columbium'. The element is found in niobite (or columbite), niobite – tantalite, pyrochlore, and euxenite. Large deposit of niobium have been found associated with carbonatites (carbon – silicate rocks) as a constituent of pyrochlore. Extensive ore reserves are found in Canada, Brazil, Nigeria, Congo and the U.S. The metal can be isolated from tantalum and prepared in several ways, it is shining, white, soft and ductile metals and takes on bluish cast when exposed to air at room temperature for a long time. The metal starts to oxidize in air at 200⁰c and when processed at even moderate temperature must be placed in a protective atmosphere. It is used as an alloying agent in carbon and alloy steel and in non – ferrous metals. These alloys have improved strength and other desirable properties.

The metals has a low capture cross section for thermal neutrons. It is used in arc – welding rods for stabilized grades of stainless steel. Thousands of pounds of niobium have been used in advanced air frame systems, such as were used in the Gemini space program. The element has superconductive properties. Superconductive magnets have been made with Nb – Zr wire, which retains its superconductivity in strong magnetic fields. This type of application offers hope of direct large – scale generation of electric power.

Tantalite and niobite $\rightarrow$ MnO, FeO, TaO₃, NbO₃, WO₃, SnO₂.

Yttrio tantalite $\rightarrow 3 (\text{CaO} \cdot \text{YO} \cdot \text{FeO}), (\text{TaO}_3, \text{WO}_3)$. The colour of these minerals is iron black. The Yttrio tantalite on boiling point become yellowish or white, that of the other remains unchanged. Acid affects them but little.

Samaraskite $\rightarrow \text{NbO}_3, \text{FeO}, \text{U}_2\text{O}_3, \text{YO}$ and is radioactive.

Microlite $\rightarrow (\text{Ca}, \text{Na})_2\text{Ta}_2\text{O}_6 (\text{O}, \text{OH}, \text{F})$; Calcium Sodium Tantalum Oxide Hydroxide Fluoride. Microlite is one of the tantalum/niobium oxides that are generally difficult to distinguish. Fortunately there are few of them that form well shaped octahedral crystals. Microlite crystallizes in the isometric symmetry class and forms fine octahedral crystals that are typically and characteristically modified by other isometric forms. Other members of the Pyrochlore Group also form octahedrons, but can sometimes be reliably differentiated by colour, streak and other characteristics. Microlite generally contains impurities of radioactive elements called rare earths and this produces the slight radioactivity in this mineral. It is occasionally placed in the informal group of minerals called the Rare Earth Oxides, but does not contain a significant amount of these metals. Microlite is an end member of solid – solution series between itself and the mineral pyrochlore from where the Pyrochlore Group gets its name. The two minerals have similar structures and properties, but microlite is the tantalum rich end member and pyrochlore is the niobium rich end member. Microlite is found mostly in granitic pegmatite dikes and more rarely in calcite rich rocks called carbonatites. The rare pyrochlore on the other hand is more common to the carbonatites and alkalic pegmatites called nepheline syenites. The mineral

gahnite also forms octahedrons but is neither a rare earth mineral nor apart of the pyrochlore Group of minerals. Gahnite is a member of the Spinel Group of oxide minerals. Its green colour makes it easy to confuse with the green varieties of microlite, but microlite is generally denser and much softer. Remember, this is a slightly radioactive mineral and should be stored away from other minerals that are subject to damage from radioactivity and of course human exposure should be limited!

Associated minerals found in microlite include quartz, feldspars, calcite, columbite, tantalite, zircon, biotite, lepidolite, spodumene and simpsonite.

6.0. EXPERIMENT PROCEDURE AND RESULTS –XRF

The tantalite and niobite used for this research work were sourced from Ijero Local Government Area of Ekiti State. They were washed properly with water and later crushed and grinded into fine powder with crushing and grinding machine in the Geology Department Laboratory University of Ado-Ekiti.

The samples (tantalite and niobite) were pelletised at the centre for energy research and development (CERD) O.A.U. Ile-Ife into a circular disk of 3cm diameter and then subjected to XRF test. (The thickness of pellets is not of interest).

The spectrometer used is EDXRF, produce by XRF system of Amptek Inc. It has XR – 100CR X – ray detector with PX4 Digital Pulse Processor MCA and Eclipse III X – ray tube and control box. The method is direct

comparison of count rates with standard count rates of analyzed elements using AXIL (Software) Calibration. Silver anode was used for the tube excitation, machine operating at 25.0KV. The live time was 1200 sec and tube current of 0.05MA the following results were obtained.

TANTALITE SAMPLE

Elements	Concentration
Ar	1.288 %W
K	trace
Ca	trace
Ti	10.699 %W
V	trace
Mn	1.546 %W
Fe	9.869 %W
Zn	trace
Rb	trace
Zr	trace
Nb	9.634 %W
Ta	12.101 %W
Pb	trace

NIOBITE SAMPLE

Elements	Concentration
Ar	trace
K	trace
Ca	trace
Ti	trace
V	trace

Elements	Concentration
Mn	2.918 %W
Fe	4.890 %W
Zn	trace
Rb	trace
Zr	2.604 % W
Nb	29.858 %W
Ta	15.885 %W
Pb	trace

Radioactive test: Using a sodium iodide (NaI(ii)) scintillation detector connected to a multichannel analyzer (at centre for energy research and development, O.A.U Ile – Ife) It shows that the samples are highly radioactive (*further radiological analysis to know the type of emission from the samples are not included in this research work*).

6.1. ELECTRICAL BEHAVIOUR

The basic parameter tested for is the resistance. From Ohm's law, it follows that

$$\frac{V}{I} = R, \text{ a constant}$$

R is defined as the 'resistance' of the conductor. The practical unit of potential difference, V, is the volt, symbol V; the practical unit of current, I, is the ampere, symbol A; the practical unit of resistance, R, is the Ohm, symbol Ω . The Ohm is thus the resistance of a conductor through which a

current of one ampere flows when a potential difference (P.d) of one volt is across it.

From the above equation; it also follows that.

$$V = IR \text{ and } I = \frac{V}{R}$$

Ohm's law states that under constant physical conditions, the potential difference across a conductor is proportional to the current through it. The law is obeyed by most important class of conductors - metals and some others, such as carbon black, it is not obeyed by some crystals, such as silicon carbide, nor by some conducting solutions, nor by thermionic valves, nor as in a neon lamp by gases.

6.2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The samples (tantalite and niobite) were pulverised and pelletised. 15mg of each sample was mixed with 5mg of industrial starch (binding agent) and a pressure of 2400 metric tons ($3.3 \times 10^{10} \text{ N/m}^2$) was applied (using hydraulic carver machine). The pellets formed were heated up to 300°C for 35 minutes in furnace so as to reduce the effect of the binding agent (to evaporate it). The pellets were later cut into a square shape of side 1.2cm and thickness of 0.3cm.

Aim: To determines the resistance of the samples.

Apparatus: A. d.c. supply

A picoammeter

1 M Ω resistor

A Voltmeter

Circuit Connection

Precaution

1. The sample was placed on a conductive silver paint to facilitate good contact.
2. 1 M Ω resistor was used to prevent excess current from getting to the sample so as to avoid damage.

By varying the voltage from the supply, the current varies and the voltage across the sample was measured.

$$\begin{aligned} V_T &= V_S + V_R \\ V_T &= \text{Voltage from the source} \\ V_R &= \text{Voltage drop across the resistor} \\ V_S &= \text{Voltage across the sample.} \end{aligned}$$

Table of Result: Tantalite Sample

V_T (V)	I (mA)	V_R (V)	V_S (V)
2.0	2.9×10^{-4}	0.24	1.76
4.0	3.3×10^{-4}	0.35	3.65
6.0	3.0×10^{-4}	.48	5.52
8.0	2.9×10^{-4}	.70	7.30
10.0	2.8×10^{-4}	.89	9.11

10.0	2.8×10^{-4}	.89	9.11
12.0	2.7×10^{-4}	1.02	10.98
14.0	2.6×10^{-4}	1.18	12.82
16.0	2.5×10^{-4}	1.30	14.70
18.0	2.1×10^{-4}	1.52	16.48
20.0	2.0×10^{-4}	1.64	18.36
22.0	1.9×10^{-4}	1.90	20.10
24.0	1.8×10^{-4}	2.10	21.90
26.0	1.8×10^{-4}	2.20	23.80
28.0	1.8×10^{-4}	2.40	25.60
30.0	1.8×10^{-4}	2.50	27.50

Table of Result: Niobite Sample

V_T (V)	I (mA)	V_R (V)	V_S (V)
2.0	1.7×10^{-4}	0.20	1.80
4.0	1.7×10^{-4}	0.40	3.60
6.0	1.6×10^{-4}	0.50	5.50
8.0	1.6×10^{-4}	0.70	7.30
10.0	1.5×10^{-4}	0.90	9.10
12.0	1.5×10^{-4}	1.10	10.90
14.0	1.4×10^{-4}	1.20	12.80
16.0	1.4×10^{-4}	1.40	14.60

18.0	1.4×10^{-4}	1.60	16.40
20.0	1.4×10^{-4}	1.70	18.30
22.0	1.3×10^{-4}	1.90	20.10
24.0	1.3×10^{-4}	2.10	21.10
26.0	1.3×10^{-4}	2.20	21.90
28.0	1.3×10^{-4}	2.40	23.80
30.0	1.2×10^{-4}	2.50	25.60

6.3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the graphs (on the back page) of voltage against current for the samples (Tantalite and Niobite), it shows that Ohm's law is disobeyed, which implies the crystals belongs to the class of conductors that fail to obeyed Ohm's law (i.e. the current across them fail to increase with voltage).

Also, from the XRF (X – ray fluorescence) technique carried out on the samples. It shows that both samples (Tantalite and Niobite) contain mostly transition elements. The tantalite sample contain about 10% titanium, 1.5% manganese, 9% iron, 9% niobium , 12% tantalum with potassium, calcium, vanadium, zinc, rubidium, zircon and lead; all in traces (ppm). The niobite as well contain about 2.9% manganese, 4.89% iron, 2.6% zircon, 29.8% niobium, 15.8% tantalum with potassium, calcium, titanium, vanadium, zinc, rubidium, and lead, all in traces (ppm). The XRF analysis clearly shows that

the samples (tantalic and niobic) contain high concentration of transition elements and the non – transition elements present in them are in traces (ppm).

Generally, transition elements show similar behaviour. They have variable valencies and the ability to form complex ion. Also, they possess high tensile strength and high melting point.

However, due to high concentration of transition elements in the samples and with their tendency to form complex ion. The electrical behaviour of the samples (from the voltage against current graph) shows that they are poor conductors and ionic conductivity is suspected to be in action.

6.4. IONIC CRYSTALS

In ionic crystals one or more electrons of one type of atoms are transferred to another, leading to the formation of positive and negative ions; for example, NaCl may be considered as to be built up of Na^+ and Cl^- ions. The cohesive energy of these crystals is to a large extent determined by the coulomb interaction between the heteropolar ions. At elevated temperatures they exhibit ionic conductivity. Associated with the existence of positive and negative ions is a strong optical absorption coefficient in the infrared. Ionic crystals may be cleaved readily. There has to be diffusion for ionic conductivity to occur in solid.

6.5. IONIC CONDUCTIVITY AND DIFFUSION

Metallic lattice in thermal equilibrium contains a certain number of lattice defects. Examples of such defects are vacant lattice sites, interstitial atoms, pairs of vacancies etc. The form of a particular type of lattice defects requires a certain energy $\emptyset$ and because the equilibrium number of defects depends on a Boltzmann factor containing $\emptyset$, those defects with lowest $\emptyset$ value will predominate. Ionic crystals should, according to thermodynamics, also contain defects in thermal equilibrium with the lattice. Here again the most common types are the vacancies and interstitial ions. Other defects are, of course, possible in principle; for example, some positive ions may occupy lattice positions that are normally occupied by negative ions. It would seem, however, that the production of such disorderly arrangements would require very high energies and thus their relative numbers would be very small. In other words, ionic crystals may be looked upon as completely ordered "alloys" (apart from vacant sites and possible interstitial ions) of a metal and a metalloid.

Let us consider an ionic crystal of the composition A^+B^- . Positive ion vacancies may then be produced in a similar way as in metals, by a number of successive jumps of positive ions. The result would be equivalent to taking a positive ion somewhere from the interior of the crystals and placing it at the surface. Suppose now that a number of positive ion vacancies would have been produced in this manner while the negative ion lattice remained perfect the surface of the crystals would then contain an excess of negative charge.

Thus space charges would be set up. It is obvious that such space charges would counteract the formation of more positive ion vacancies. On the other hand, the field set up by the space charges would favour the formation of negative ion vacancies. We thus conclude that as a consequence of the tendency to prevent the build – up of space charges, ionic crystals should contain nearly equal numbers of positive and negative ion vacancies. Thus even if the energy ϕ required to produce a single positive ion vacancy, they would occur in approximately equal numbers in the interior of the crystal. It is obvious from this that their number will be determined only by the sum of the formation energies.

$$\phi = \phi_+ + \phi_-$$

It will be evident that a positive and a negative ion vacancy will attract each other as a result of the coulomb field between them. For large distances, the energy of attraction is equal to $-e^2/Er$, where E is the dielectric constant of the medium. They may therefore combine to form pairs of vacancies. At a given temperature there will exist a certain ratio between the number of pairs, the ratio depending on the dissociation depending on whether the distance between the single vacancies is small or large; thermally excited state of a pair if the distance between the vacancies is only a few atomic diameters.

Interstitial ions in combination with vacancies may also occur: for example, a positive ion may jump into an interstitial position, leaving a vacancy behind. If the vacancy and interstitial ion are far enough apart to

prevent an immediate recombination, one speaks of Frenkel defects. In this case it is not necessary to have equal numbers of positives and negative Frenkel defects, because their formation does not require the setting up of space charges over macroscopic distances. In general, depending essentially on the energy required to form them, either the positive or negative Frenkel defects will predominate.

It is evident that diffusion of ions in a perfect lattice, i.e. in a lattice in which all lattice sites are occupied by the proper ions, is impossible because a given ion has no place to go. Diffusion is therefore possible only by the migration of interstitial ions or by the migration of vacant lattice sites. For instance, in alkali halides lattice, vacancies are the predominant type of defects. Thus the positive ions surrounding a positive ions vacancy may jump into the latter; consequently, the vacancy moves through the crystal by virtue of positive ions jumping into it and diffusion becomes possible.

6.6. IONIC CONDUCTIVITY IN 'PURE' IONIC CRYSTALS (ALKALI HALIDE)

When a potential difference is applied between two opposite faces of an ionic crystal, an electric current may be detected. For alkali halides these currents are too large to be explained in terms of the motion of electrons because the number of electrons in the conduction band for the temperatures involved would be much too small. Thus the currents must be a result of the migration of ions under the influence of the electric field, similar to the

electrolytic conduction of aqueous solutions of salts. That the currents are indeed of an ionic nature is also indicated by the fact that decomposition occurs at the electrodes.

The first problems which arises is to determine which constituent carries the current. Although the actual experiments are usually more involved, this question may be answered in principle by employing an experimental arraignment as indicated in fig. 24.

Fig. 24. Essential experimental arrangement for measuring transport numbers

Two slabs of a salt M^+X^- are pressed together between two electrodes of the metal M . for the polarity as indicated, the two following extreme possibilities exist:

- i) Only positive ions move; in that case the cathode will grow at the expenses of the anode, the thickness of the two salts slabs remaining the same.
- ii) Only the negative ions move; the X^- ions are then neutralized at the anode and form new layers of salt. Hence the anode decreases in

thickness, the cathode increase. Furthermore, slab 1 will grow at the expense of slab 2.

If both types of ions contribute to the current, the result will be intermediate between (i) and (ii). By weighing, the relative contributions to the ionic current by the positive and negative ions may be determined.

The ionic conductivity of an isotropic crystal is defined by the scalar equation

$$I = \delta E$$

Where

$$I = \text{Current density}$$
$$E = \text{Field strength}$$
$$\delta = \text{Conductivity}$$

If the conductivity of the positive ions alone is δ_+ , the transport number of these ions is defined by

$$t_+ = \delta_+ / \delta$$

Similarly, $t_- = \delta_- / \delta$

and of course $t_+ + t_- = 1$

6.7. IONIC CONDUCTIVITY IN ALKALI HALIDES WITH ADDED DIVALENT IMPURITIES

It is possible to grow crystals of alkali halides or silver halides with intentionally added small amounts of the halides of divalent metals, such as Sr, Ba or Ca. The density of crystals of KCl containing small amounts of CaCl_2 and SrCl_2 has been measured by Pick and Weber (A. J. Dekker, page 178). The results demonstrate that the divalent ions are incorporated

substitutionally, i.e. they occupy lattice sites which are normally occupied by the monovalent alkali ions.

In figure 25. Gives an example of the influence of the divalent ions on the conductivity some results obtained by Kelting and Wilt (A.J. Dekker, page 178-179). The logarithm of conductivity δ has been plotted versus $1/T$ for a 'pure' crystals of KCl (curves 7 and 8) and KCl with different amounts of SrCl₂. We note that all curves come together to a single straight line, the intrinsic region. In that region, the conductivity is determined essentially by the density of vacancies produced thermally. Now for each divalent ion there is one positive ion vacancy. Consequently, at low temperatures the number of vacancies per unit volume remains constant and is equal to the density of divalent metal ions. At a given temperature, the experiments show that the 'induced' conductivity nearly proportional to the concentration of the divalent metal. The importance of measurements of this kind lies in the fact that they permit us to determine.

- i. The mobility of the positive ion vacancies.
- ii. The density of schottky defects in the intrinsic range.
- iii. The binding energy of a divalent impurity and a positive ion vacancy.

This follows from the following consideration: When the conductivity δ and the concentration of charge carriers n are known, the mobility μ (i.e., the velocity per unit field may be calculated from the relation

$$\delta = ne\mu.$$

we may finally mention the influence of divalent positive ions on the dielectric losses of alkali halides. The associated complex of a divalent ion and a vacancy corresponds to a dipole. The direction of this dipole may change as a result of the jumping of the vacancy as well as by the interchange of divalent ion and the vacancy.

Figure 25. The ionic conductivity of KCl crystals containing various amounts of SrCl₂. In Unit of 10⁻⁵ the numbers refer to the following mole fractions: $M_1 = 19$; $M_2 = 8.7$; $M_3 = 6.1$; $M_4 = 3.5$; $M_5 = 1.9$; $M_6 = 1.2$; $M_{7,8} = 0$.

CONCLUSION

From the research work carried out on Ijero Ekiti Tantalite and Niobite in this project. It shows that the concentration of the tantalum in the tantalite is 12%w and the niobium in the niobite is 29%w. The samples (tantalite and niobite) also contain mostly transition elements as impurities and they appear radioactive. However, they belong to the class of crystals that fail to obey Ohm's law and it implies they might possibly exhibit ionic conductivity due to oxides or vacancy impurities. The transition elements in the samples (tantalite and niobite), and their abilities to exist in variable oxidation states, with tendencies to form complex ion and their radioactive nature may explain the negative ohmic characteristic exhibited by the samples.

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Lu La 2.275E+004 ± 1.100E+000
 Hf La 2.694E+004 ± 1.303E+000
 Ta La 3.209E+004 ± 1.552E+000
 W La 3.847E+004 ± 1.861E+000
 Re La 4.640E+004 ± 2.244E+000
 Os La 5.629E+004 ± 2.722E+000
 Ir La 6.872E+004 ± 3.323E+000
 Pt La 8.439E+004 ± 4.081E+000
 Au La 1.043E+005 ± 5.043E+000
 Hg La 1.296E+005 ± 6.269E+000
 Tl La 1.621E+005 ± 7.841E+000
 Pb La 2.040E+005 ± 9.866E+000
 Bi La 2.583E+005 ± 1.249E+001

Sample: C:\AXIL\SPECT\BALOGUN\355-2809.ASR

Measurement date: 09-28-2006

Live time: 1200 sec

Tube current: 0.050 mA

Method is Direct comparison of count rates

Analysed elements:

El	counts	compound	conc
Ar Ka	6357 ± 128	Ar	7883.185 ± 819.515 ppm
K Ka	11071 ± 242	K	9788.683 ± 2282.423 ppm
Ca Ka	43506 ± 415	Ca	2.736 ± 0.240 %w
Ti Ka	9964 ± 153	Ti	3247.295 ± 344.953 ppm
Mn Ka	30827 ± 206	Mn	4459.925 ± 428.046 ppm
Fe Ka	1486800 ± 1155	Fe	17.725 ± 0.923 %w
Cu Ka	8794 ± 130	Cu	820.642 ± 50.584 ppm
Zn Ka	3170 ± 109	Zn	312.994 ± 37.351 ppm
As Ka	7688 ± 150	As	1509.227 ± 92.270 ppm
Pb Ka	509 ± 68	Rb	<1212.908
Sr Ka	872 ± 67	Sr	4796.479 ± 586.837 ppm
Sn La	50028 ± 288	Sn	31.417 ± 0.783 %w
W La	8078 ± 94	W	3499.697 ± 121.288 ppm
Pb La	1469 ± 90	Pb	120.016 ± 12.543 ppm
Bi La	923 ± 63	Bi	59.556 ± 8.241 ppm

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Sample: C:\AXIL\SPECT\BALOGUN\DATA-2-1.ASR (tantalite)

Measurement date: 00-00- 0

Live time: 1200 sec 20 min

Tube current: 0.050 mA

Method is Direct comparison of count rates

Analysed elements:

El	counts	compound	conc
Ar Ka	9096 ± 242	Ar	1.128 ± 0.192 %w
K Ka	3677 ± 225	K	<6363.311
Ca Ka	4385 ± 220	Ca	2757.862 ± 262.340 ppm
Ti Ka	328277 ± 615	Ti	10.699 ± 0.551 %w
V Ka	11976 ± 302	V	2887.314 ± 291.287 ppm

QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS REPORT

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Report created on: 09-29-2006

Calibration file: C:\AXIL\SPECT\BALOGUN\355-LK.cal

Created on: 09-29-2006

Tube excitation: Ag Anode Operating at: 25.0 KV

Method used: DIRECT COMPARISON OF COUNT RATES

El standard count rates

Ar	Ka	1.344E+004	±	6.892E+002
K	Ka	1.885E+004	±	9.668E+002
Ca	Ka	2.650E+004	±	1.359E+003
Sc	Ka	3.706E+004	±	1.900E+003
Ti	Ka	5.114E+004	±	2.622E+003
V	Ka	6.913E+004	±	3.545E+003
Cr	Ka	9.084E+004	±	4.658E+003
Mn	Ka	1.152E+005	±	5.906E+003
Fe	Ka	1.398E+005	±	7.169E+003
Co	Ka	1.613E+005	±	8.269E+003
Ni	Ka	1.754E+005	±	8.995E+003
Cu	Ka	1.786E+005	±	9.156E+003
Zn	Ka	1.688E+005	±	8.657E+003
Ga	Ka	1.471E+005	±	7.545E+003
Ge	Ka	1.173E+005	±	6.015E+003
As	Ka	8.490E+004	±	4.354E+003
Se	Ka	5.537E+004	±	2.839E+003
Br	Ka	3.228E+004	±	1.655E+003
Kr	Ka	1.670E+004	±	8.564E+002
Rb	Ka	7.610E+003	±	3.902E+002
Sr	Ka	3.030E+003	±	1.554E+002
Y	Ka	1.047E+003	±	5.367E+001
Zr	Ka	3.112E+002	±	1.596E+001
Nb	Ka	7.904E+001	±	4.053E+000
Mo	Ka	1.702E+001	±	8.727E-001
Tc	Ka	3.084E+000	±	1.581E-001
In	La	2.561E+003	±	1.239E-001
Sn	La	2.654E+003	±	1.283E-001
Sb	La	2.767E+003	±	1.338E-001
Te	La	2.902E+003	±	1.403E-001
I	La	3.062E+003	±	1.481E-001
Xe	La	3.251E+003	±	1.572E-001
Cs	La	3.472E+003	±	1.679E-001
Ba	La	3.731E+003	±	1.804E-001
La	La	4.034E+003	±	1.951E-001
Ce	La	4.388E+003	±	2.122E-001
Pr	La	4.802E+003	±	2.322E-001
Nd	La	5.287E+003	±	2.557E-001
Pm	La	5.856E+003	±	2.832E-001
Sm	La	6.527E+003	±	3.156E-001
Eu	La	7.318E+003	±	3.539E-001
Gd	La	8.256E+003	±	3.992E-001
Tb	La	9.370E+003	±	4.531E-001

Ta La	232987 ± 340	Ta	12.101 ± 0.270	%w
Pb La	1116 ± 64	Pb	91.176 ± 11.657	ppm

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Sample: C:\AXIL\SPECT\BALOGUN\BATA2--1.ASR ~~(2.11.10)~~ *Columbite*

Measurement date: 00-00- 0

Live time: 1200 sec

Tube current: 0.050 mA

Method is Direct comparison of count rates

Analysed elements:

El	counts	compound	conc
Ar Ka	5724 ± 131	Ar	7098.214 ± 694.568 ppm
K Ka	7453 ± 136	K	6589.744 ± 2154.782 ppm
Ca Ka	13864 ± 162	Ca	8719.496 ± 981.460 ppm
Ti Ka	9008 ± 149	Ti	2935.732 ± 170.082 ppm
V Ka	2342 ± 126	V	564.637 ± 52.778 ppm
Mn Ka	201665 ± 469	Mn	2.918 ± 0.150 %w
Fe Ka	410213 ± 648	Fe	4.890 ± 0.255 %w
Zn Ka	53490 ± 266	Zn	5281.398 ± 283.051 ppm
Rb Ka	510 ± 72	Rb	1116.951 ± 322.466 ppm
Zr Ka	15206 ± 132	Zr	2.604 ± 0.064 %w
Nb Ka	131136 ± 340	Nb	29.858 ± 0.439 %w
Ta La	305851 ± 385	Ta	15.885 ± 0.352 %w
Pb La	1292 ± 75	Pb	105.556 ± 16.792 ppm

TANTALITE XRF SPECT

Columbite XRF SPEC

GRAPH OF VOLTAGE AGAINST CURRENT ACROSS TANTALITE SAMPLE

The slope of the graph of voltage against current across tantalite sample.

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Slope} &= \frac{\Delta V_s}{\Delta I} = \frac{25.60 - 5.52}{(1.8 \times 10^{-4} - 3.0 \times 10^{-4}) \times 10^{-3}} \frac{\text{V}}{\text{A}} \\ &= \frac{20.08}{-0.00000012} = -167333333.3 \Omega\end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore -167333333.3 \Omega \approx -1.6 \times 10^8 \Omega$$

GRAPH OF VOLTAGE AGAINST CURRENT ACROSS NIOBITE SAMPLE

The slope of the graph of voltage against current across niobite sample.

$$\text{Slope} = \frac{\Delta V_s}{\Delta I} = \frac{25.60 - 1.80}{(1.2 \times 10^{-4} - 1.7 \times 10^{-4}) \times 10^{-3}} \frac{\text{V}}{\text{A}}$$

$$= \frac{23.8}{-0.00000005} = -476000000 \Omega$$

$$\therefore -476000000 \Omega \approx -4.7 \times 10^8 \Omega$$